

High Temperature Nanocomposite Insulation for High Power Density Machines

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Abstract— Increasing demand for higher power, lighter weight and compact power generation systems in aircraft has resulted in the need for a new high temperature insulation system. It requires better thermal capability and improved reliability over the 240°C system used commercially. A 280°C insulation system has been developed based on a hybrid organic-inorganic material to address these evolving requirements. This electrical insulation system comprises a nanocomposite polyimide wire for windings, and a hybrid slot liner for ground wall insulation. Thermal, electrical and mechanical properties of this insulation system will be discussed.

Keywords— Magnet wire, slot liner, thermal stability, pulse resistance, voltage endurance, power density, electric machine, high temperature, hybrid insulation, nanocomposite.

I. INTRODUCTION

The trend in modern electric machine design is toward increased power density and efficiency in operation. These requirements are particularly demanding in the more electric architectures of modern aircraft power systems, due to the weight and space limitations inherent to aviation applications. Therefore, electrical insulation materials are required which are reliable at higher temperatures and in harsh environments.

In Aerospace applications, progressive electrification of on-board services is a way to reduce or to remove the dependence on hydraulic, mechanical and bleed air/pneumatic systems. In addition to the more electric aircraft (MEA) concept, the more Electric Engine (MEE) concept has developed in which electrical machines, such as starters and generators, are integrated into the engine architecture [1]. Such motors and generators must be designed to operate in harsh environmental conditions. Temperatures in the nacelle can be higher than 350°C, an extreme challenge for both conductor and insulation materials typically used for machine windings [2].

One approach to managing increased temperatures is to employ a more capable cooling system, but this typically comes with additional cost, mass, and system complexity. Another method is to decrease the thermal resistance of the insulation, which can be done by increasing the thermal conductivity of insulation materials, or reducing insulation thickness without compromising dielectric withstand capability. A third approach is to employ insulation capable of higher operating temperatures, to allow reliable operation despite the added thermal load from increased power density.

Since the introduction of variable frequency drives (VFD) with pulse width modulated (PWM) waveforms using IGBT

technology, more and more motors are powered with VFD for energy efficiency. This is true for aviation generators as well. In this application, the combined stresses from high frequency, high voltage and high temperature at low atmospheric pressure can severely degrade insulation materials, shortening insulation life and system reliability. Windings that can withstand high temperature and endure corona attack are required to achieve maximum power density without requiring a complex cooling system. It is also desired to have a thin insulation coating for the winding to achieve maximum copper fill in the machine. Therefore, an advanced high temperature insulation material is desired to withstand high voltages in thin, mechanically robust layers. GE has developed high temperature wire coatings with nanocomposite technology and organic-inorganic hybrid structures. The development has scaled through iterations of coating solution formulation to film evaluation, then to wire coating, winding evaluation, and finally full system trials. The wire with this nanocomposite coating can be run continuously at temperatures up to 300°C (60°C higher than Kapton® polyimide) and last 10 times longer in life under repetitive electrical pulses where partial discharge is present. The organic-inorganic hybrid film developed has been proved to have continuous use temperature up to 320°C (80°C higher than Kapton® film).

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Magnet wire coating

The magnet wire coating is comprised of a polyimide polymer containing phenylalkoxysilane treated alumina nanoparticles. In the lab development, nanoparticles were surface treated by ultrasonication in a solvent mixture of anhydrous toluene and an anhydrous alcohol, followed by refluxing for 3 hours. The treated, filtered nanoparticles were then suspended in a polar solvent compatible with the polyamic acid solution which forms the wire coating base. The resulting solution was coated and cured on 22AWG copper magnet wire in a traditional wire enamel coating process.

B. Slot liner

High temperature stable polyimide films were employed as slot liners. To further improve the thermal stability, inorganic barrier coatings such as Si_3N_4 or SiO_2 were deposited on both faces of the film as barrier layers to reduce thermo-oxidative degradation at high temperature. a Si_xN_y layer 50-100nm thick was deposited using a PlasmaTherm 790 reactor with 2% SiH_4 diluted in helium, and ammonia (NH_3). SiO_2 of 50~100nm

was deposited using A Perkin Elmer 4450 RF magnetron sputter chamber equipped with SiO₂ target.

C. Thermal endurance test

Thermo-gravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to obtain the thermal index of insulation materials according to ASTM D1932. Samples were cast from the enamel solution, and cured to remove solvent and produce a fully-imidized film. The weight losses of the films were measured under different heating rates. The activation energies of degradation were calculated based on the Arrhenius equation. The temperature at which the material loses 5% of its original weight over 20,000 hours is defined as thermal index (TI), and 60,000 hours as therelative thermal index (RTI) of the material.

Coated wires were tested as well, comparing the nanocomposite polyimide and commercially available polyimide enamel. Frames with twisted pairs of these two wire types (see Figure 1) were placed in three different ovens, with temperatures set at 300°C, 320°C and 340°C respectively. They were removed at proscribed times and subjected to a 600 V AC hipot test to check for electrical shorts between turns in the twisted pairs. The end of life is defined as the aging time at the temperature when the wire failed the 600V test according to ASTM D2307. An Arrhenius plot of the data was used to extrapolate the end of life for intended service temperatures. The maximum service temperature or relative thermal index (RTI) of the 22AWG is defined as the temperature at which the wire survives for 20,000 hours without failing under the application of 600V.

Fig.1 Wire frame for thermal endurance tests

Fig.2 Pulse endurance test set-up

D. Pulse endurance test

A custom built high voltage (HV) pulse generator was employed to measure wire performance under 20 kHz square

wave pulsed voltages of positive polarity. The dV/dt of the pulses is about 20kV/μs. The typical pulse waveform is shown in Figure 2. The HV electrode was connected to one end of the twisted pair and the ground electrode was connected to other end of the same twisted pair. The time to failure was recorded for each voltage level.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Polyimide film is commonly used in aviation motors and generators for the slot liner and phase separator. Dielectric properties of polyimide films at elevated temperatures are affected by the thermal stability of the materials [3]. Our previous work [4] has indicated that the breakdown voltage of polyimide film suffers from thermo-oxidative degradation. To protect polyimide from thermo-oxidative degradation, we applied thin inorganic barrier coatings of silicon nitride and silicon dioxide, as shown in Figure 3. This hybrid inorganic-organic polyimide film showed much better thermal resistance, as evidenced by the higher decomposition temperature of the polyimide film with 80nm Si_xN_y coatings (see Figure 4) by TGA. The improvement in thermal stability by inorganic coating is even more noticeable under isothermal aging. Figure 5 shows the remaining weight of films after thermal aging at 320°C for more than 8000 hrs.

Furthermore, the mechanical strength of the Upilex-S® films was tested after thermal aging at 350°C. As shown in Figure 6, Upilex-S® film with Si_xN_y coating maintained more than 50% of its original strength after 1000 hours aging at 350°C. This supports the hypothesis that a thin but continuous inorganic coating on the polymer film will slow thermo-oxidative degradation, and maintain the film's properties and integrity at temperature. As a rule of thumb, every ten degrees of temperature rise will cut the insulation life by half. It is expected that silicon nitride coated Upilex-S® film can last more than 20,000 hours at 300°C.

Fig.3 TEM picture of hybrid film

Fig.4 Thermal stability comparison by TGA

Fig.5 Thermal stability comparison by weight loss at 320°C aging

Fig.6 Tensile strength of Polyimide films after thermal aging at 350°C

Adding nano-particles in the polymer matrix can improve its thermal stability as well as corona resistance. Small percentages of alumina nanoparticles were incorporated in polyamic acid solutions. Films cast from the composite solutions were compared to the base polymer films for thermal stability. TGA was used to obtain the thermal index of these films, as previously described. Commercial state-of-the-art Pyre-ML solution, widely used for polyimide magnet wire coating, was compared as a benchmark. A polyamic acid precursor of different chemistry is used for improved thermal capability in the nanoparticle enhanced resin as well. As indicated in Table 1, the film cast from the experimental solutions provides a 45°C higher thermal index than traditional Pyre-ML polyimide. Addition of a small percentage of alumina nanoparticles in the polyimide matrix further improves its thermal stability. In the case of silane treated nano alumina in the high-temperature polyimide, the measured thermal index is over 300°C, which is more than 60°C higher than Kapton® and ML polyimide. This polyimide alumina nanocomposite has been applied on plain copper conductor, unlike conventional high temperature wire coated on nickle-cladded copper. This provides the advantage of higher conductivity and current carrying capability. The magnet wire thus made was tested for its thermal stability. The thermal endurance test was performed according to the ASTM D2307 test as described earlier, with 22 AWG wires samples made with high-temp polyimide with alumina nanocomposite (HTHF wire) and Pyre-ML polyimide (ML wire). Figure 7 (the life vs. stress curve was plotted in logarithmic scale)

shows the thermal endurance curve. The control samples only lasted less than 200 hours at 320°C, could not be plotted into curve. The thermal index for the HTHF wire is about 290°C which is lower than 307°C projected for high temperature polyimide alumina nanocomposite (see Table 1,) by the TGA method. The discrepancy in (TI) between the film sample and the wire sample is believed to be caused by Cu diffusion in wire coating at test temperatures.

TABLE I. THERMAL STABILITY COMPARISON OF NANOCOMPOSITE POLYIMIDE FILMS BY TGA

Insulations	Temp @ 5wt% loss, °C	TI, 20,000 hrs	RTI, 60,000 hrs
ML control polyimide	492.3	240	224
High-temp polyimide	559.8	286	269
ML-polyimide /Al ₂ O ₃	544.4	262	246
High-temp polyimide /Al ₂ O ₃	569.3	307	291

Fig.7 Thermal endurance results of HTHF wire

Fig.8 Pictures of ML wires and HTHF wires after thermal aging at 320°C for 168 hours (left) and at 340°C for 72 hours (right)

Stators wound with coils made of control ML wires with ML-Pyre polyimide and HTHF wires with polyimide alumina nanocomposite were also tested for thermal aging side-by-side. Figure 8 shows wire status before and after thermal aging. At 320°C and 340°C all ML wires have completely degraded and charred after short time, while HTHF wire is still intact.

The electrical performance, especially the pulse endurance of the wire under PWM drive conditions, is of interest for the

aviation generator. The time to failure under pulsed voltages with rise time of 20 kV/ μ s and repetitive frequency of 20 kHz was measured. As shown in Figure 9, the red curve represents measured results of the high temperature wire made of HTHF enamel solution and the blue curve represent results of the control wires made of Pyre-ML polyimide solution. Different electric stress levels were applied on the twisted pairs, with higher stress causing more pronounced corona on the wire surface, shown by the green lighted area in the pictures next to the curves (the pictures were taken with corona scope). The average corona inception stress is around 570V/mil for the control wire and about 620V/mil for the nanocomposite HTHF wire. At the same stress level, for example, at 500V/mil, the time to failure of the nanocomposite HTHF wire is more than ten times longer than that of the benchmark polyimide wire.

Fig.9 Pulse endurance of ML (blue curve) wire and HTHF wire (red curve)

The significant improvement shown on both thermal and electrical performance in nanocomposite polyimide film and wire coating can be explained as following: 1) High surface area of nanoparticles creates a large interfacial interaction zone within polymer matrix, creating a short-range highly immobilized layer near the surface of the nanoparticles [6]. This layer restricts the polymer chain movement around the nanoparticles, thus changing the polymer chain kinetic energy. Nanoparticles are evenly distributed in the polymer matrix as shown in Figure 10, and act as local immobilizer or anchors for the polymer similar to a crosslinking network. Therefore, the thermal stability of the polymer matrix is enhanced. 2) Nano-sized alumina particles and its surrounding interfacial layer might also alter the electric field around them. Electron charge mobility might be slowed by the presence of nanoparticles in the polymer region preventing direct polymer chain breakage from electron bombardment by corona. This provides improved reliability of a motor/generator driven by a pulse width modulated inverter. It is known that high dV/dt and high frequency of pulsed voltages add significant electric stress to the winding insulation.

Fig.10 SEM picture of HTHF wire coating

The wire coating integrity is also critical for long-term performance of an electric machine. Any cracks during winding manufacturing and machine assembly can severely degrade the machine performance. The HTHF wire was evaluated in the coil form and in a stator assembly. It has successfully passed all manufacturing process and shown excellent robustness for machine winding process and motor assembly. The coating can be applied on both round and rectangular copper wires, as shown in Figure 11.

Fig.11 Stator and rotor built with HTHF wire and hybrid film

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